

Bilateral Tumor Infiltration of the Optic Nerve in a Patient with Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia (ALL) with Central Nervous System (CNS) Involvement: Case Report

Alma Rosa Flores Rivera*¹, Emmanuel Contreras Ortega², Oscar David Sanchez Ibarra³

¹Department of Ophthalmology, Hospital de Especialidades, Centro Médico Nacional de Occidente, Instituto Mexicano del Seguro Social, Guadalajara, Jalisco, México.

²Neuro-Ophthalmology and Oculoplastics Division, Department of Ophthalmology, Hospital de Especialidades, Centro Médico Nacional de Occidente, Instituto Mexicano del Seguro Social, Guadalajara, Jalisco, México.

³Department of Internal Medicine, Hospital de Especialidades, Centro Médico Nacional de Occidente, Instituto Mexicano del Seguro Social, Guadalajara, Jalisco, México.

ABSTRACT

Leukemic infiltration of the optic nerve is a rare but serious manifestation of acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL), particularly when involving the central nervous system (CNS). We report the case of a 23-year-old woman with a history of ALL in remission who presented with binocular diplopia, vertigo, and a central scotoma. Ophthalmic examination revealed bilateral optic disc edema, and cerebrospinal fluid analysis confirmed CNS relapse. The patient underwent intrathecal chemotherapy with subsequent improvement in visual function and reduction of optic nerve infiltration. This case underscores the importance of prompt recognition of visual symptoms in ALL survivors, as they may signal CNS involvement requiring urgent intervention.

KEYWORDS: Optic nerve infiltration, Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia, Leukemic retinopathy, Relapse, Optic disc edema.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL) is a malignant hematologic condition characterized by proliferation of immature lymphoid cells within the bone marrow and peripheral blood, it represents approximately 70% of all leukemia diagnoses. The bone marrow is the most common site of recurrence, occurring in 50% to 60% of cases, followed by the central nervous system (CNS) in approximately 20%.

Ocular involvement is a well-recognized form of extramedullary relapse in leukemia, with reported incidence rates ranging from 9% to 90%. While retinal and choroidal infiltration are more frequently observed, optic nerve involvement is less common but clinically significant, often indicating CNS dissemination. Importantly, optic nerve infiltration may occur as an isolated sign of relapse, highlighting the need for prompt recognition and potentially localized treatment, such as radiation therapy.

We describe a case of a young-adult patient with a history of ALL in remission with bilateral optic nerve infiltration as initial manifestation of ALL relapse with CNS involvement.

II. CASE REPORT

A 23-year-old female with a history of ALL L2 subtype according to the FAB classification, pre-B cell phenotype, CD20 positive, diagnosed in December 2015, currently in remission, was admitted to our hospital. She presented with complaints of diplopia, photopsia, acute vertigo accompanied by tinnitus, and sudden, painless visual loss in the right eye, initially manifesting as a temporal scotoma that progressively extended to complete visual field loss.

On initial examination, there was no light perception in the right eye (RE), while visual acuity in the left eye (LE) was 20/140. The anterior segment evaluation was unremarkable. However, fundoscopic examination revealed marked optic disc pallor with blurred margins, creamy white infiltrates over it with multiple peripapillary flame-shaped hemorrhages,

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moderate dot and blot hemorrhages in the macular region with hard exudates, as well as significant venous dilation and tortuosity. The left eye exhibited a comparable fundus appearance, though with less pronounced optic disc pallor and margin blurring, and with minimal to no posterior pole hemorrhages.

The patient was admitted under the care of the Hematology and Oncology service. Laboratory studies, including immunophenotyping, demonstrated the following profile: CD34+, CD45+, CD20+, CD19+, CD38+, CD9+, CD58+, CD123+, CD81+, CD66c+, CD10+, with negative expression for CD15 and CD33. Cerebrospinal fluid cytology was positive for malignant cells, revealing infiltration by immature-appearing blasts consistent with acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL).

Induction therapy was initiated three days after ophthalmologic evaluation, consisting of Rituximab 525 mg, Vincristine 2 mg, and Dexamethasone 40 mg IV, followed by intrathecal chemotherapy with Cytarabine 100 mg, Dexamethasone 8 mg, and Methotrexate 12 mg. Radiotherapy was not performed. Orbital Computed tomography (CT) scans revealed no relevant abnormalities. (Figure 1). Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) with contrast was advised but ultimately not performed due to technical malfunction of the MRI system.

A post-treatment bone marrow biopsy demonstrated granulocytic series with maturation to segmented neutrophils, sparse paratrabeular precursors, and normoblastic erythroid maturation with central colony formation. No lymphoblasts were identified. Immunohistochemistry for terminal deoxynucleotidyl transferase (TdT) showed 1% positivity.

After one month of treatment, visual acuity improved to 20/140 in the RE and 20/40 in the LE. Fundoscopy revealed marked improvement of papilledema and venous tortuosity, though peripapillary hemorrhages persisted in the right eye, while the left eye demonstrated mild residual papilledema. (Figure 2). At an 8-week follow-up, final best-corrected visual acuity was 20/400 in the RE and 20/50 in LE. Fundus examination showed resolution of disc edema, well-defined disc margins, mild optic disc pallor, and sparse hemorrhages in the right eye, with similar findings in the left eye, accompanied by persistent hard exudates in the macular region.

A diagnosis of bilateral leukemic optic nerve infiltration was established. The patient remained under oncologic follow-up; however, seven months after presentation, she developed pneumonia as a complication and subsequently died.

Figure 1. CT scan with two sections allowing visualization of the optic nerve pathways in the right and left eyes, without evidence of thickening.

Figure 2. (a) Fundus photographs at initial presentation (right and left eye, respectively) demonstrate marked optic disc pallor and edema, venous tortuosity, retinal hemorrhages, and hard exudates. (b) Fundus photographs obtained four weeks after initiation of intrathecal chemotherapy reveal partial resolution of disc edema and venous dilation. (c) Final fundus photographs at eight weeks show a decrease in retinal flame-shaped hemorrhages in the right eye, optic disc exhibiting mild pallor; in the left eye, residual sectoral blurring of the nasal disc margin is observed.

III. DISCUSSION

Optic nerve infiltration as an initial manifestation of leukemia relapse is an uncommon finding, reported in approximately 5% to 13% of cases. This rare presentation is thought to arise from the unique vulnerability of the eyes and optic nerves, which act as pharmacological sanctuaries during leukemia treatment. The blood-retinal barrier (BRB) restricts

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the penetration of systemically administered chemotherapeutic agents into the central nervous system, thereby facilitating leukemic persistence and relapse in ocular tissues.

Ocular involvement may initially be subtle, with impaired visual acuity sometimes representing the sole clinical manifestation of leukemic infiltration. Notably, relapse in adult acute leukemia tends to involve posterior segment structures more frequently, whereas childhood acute leukemia more often affects the anterior segment. Such variability highlights the need for clinicians to remain vigilant for ocular signs of relapse in patients with acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL), even during clinical remission. Importantly, alternative etiologies of visual loss—including opportunistic infections, vasculitis, radiotherapy-induced changes, or adverse drug reactions—must be carefully excluded. Diagnostic work-up should consistently include lumbar puncture, alongside ophthalmologic and radiologic assessment, to establish the underlying cause.

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) with contrast is considered the most sensitive modality for detecting leukemic infiltration of the optic nerve. However, normal MRI findings do not preclude the diagnosis. Several reports describe confirmed cases of leukemic optic neuropathy based primarily on clinical, ophthalmologic, and cytological evidence, even in the absence of radiologic abnormalities. A definitive diagnosis in this case was based on a comprehensive integration of clinical, ophthalmic, and hematologic findings. The patient presented with sudden, painless visual loss, characteristic fundoscopic features of optic disc edema, hemorrhages, and venous tortuosity, alongside cerebrospinal fluid positive for malignant blasts—consistent with central nervous system leukemia. These findings support the diagnosis of central nervous system leukemia despite unremarkable imaging, underscoring the limitations of MRI in this context.

From a therapeutic standpoint, adjunctive local radiotherapy has often been reported as the treatment of choice for leukemic optic nerve infiltration. In the present case, radiotherapy was suggested but not performed; instead, the patient received intrathecal chemotherapy alone, which led to moderate visual improvement compared with the initial presentation. This outcome emphasizes the importance of individualized therapeutic strategies, as well as the potential for functional recovery even when radiotherapy is not applied.

Nevertheless, ocular involvement in leukemia remains a true neuro-oncologic emergency, not only due to the risk of irreversible vision loss but also because it is associated with significantly reduced overall survival, often less than 24 months.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This case highlights the critical importance of considering optic nerve infiltration in patients with acute lymphoblastic leukemia who present with unexplained visual loss, even during remission. Recognizing this manifestation as an indicator of central nervous system relapse is essential, as timely diagnosis and appropriate intervention can mitigate irreversible ocular damage and potentially improve overall survival.

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